

RESULTS OF ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN KIDNEYS AS A RESULT OF SEVERE POLYTRAUMA.

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Summary: This article presents information about the results of scientific studies that allow us to evaluate and study the morphological features of the kidneys of 3-month-old rats after severe brain injury.

Keywords: traumatic brain injury, kidneys, nephron, biopsy, Shumlyansky-Bowman's capsule, vascular glomerulus.

Abstract: According to the researchers of the world, it is important to assess the severity, duration and duration of mechanical injury in polytrauma patients based on reactive changes in the body, inflammation, regeneration and the pathomorphological state of the amount of injured tissues [1]. Kidneys are one of the most injured organs in response to mechanical injury caused by polytrauma, and it is the organ that develops clear pathomorphological changes [2]. Up to now, the number of diseases with impaired kidney function is increasing. The main reasons for the increase in the number of diseases are the development of various complications in the kidneys due to the lack of timely diagnosis, treatment and preventive measures of primary diseases. In particular, the study of the structure and functional properties of the kidney remains an urgent problem in the field of modern urology and nephrology, because the kidneys have a complex structure and function compared to other members of the urinary system. Information about the morphological changes in the kidney caused by biological, physical, human and mechanical factors, as well as the changes that occur under the influence of stress conditions and especially severe polytrauma, has been little studied. This shows that polytrauma and subsequent kidney complications are not only a medical, but also an economic and social problem, and it is an urgent task to find a solution to it.

Materials and methods: Three-month-old white rats with an average weight of 150 g were obtained for this study. All laboratory animals were housed in a vivarium in plastic cages lined with wood chips at room temperature with a 12-h light-dark cycle, in accordance with laboratory animal care standards. The animals of the experimental group were divided into 2 groups, i.e., the first group included animals without spinal cord injury (control, n=5), and the second group (experimental n=5) included animals with severe

polytrauma. In the study, severe polytrauma was inflicted on white rats using a specially developed model, using the "traffic accident" method.

During this experiment, all animals suffered serious injuries due to severe polytrauma. After the injury, the surviving animals were transferred to a special plastic cage and observed until recovery of the post-traumatic condition.

Results of the study: in the analysis of changes in the kidneys of 3-month-old white rats after severe polytrauma, the following data were obtained: Macroscopically, the kidneys of 3-month-old white rats of the experimental group are red-brown and bean-shaped . located in the lumbar region, covered with a smooth and shiny capsule from the outside, no pathological changes visible from the macroscopic side were observed . Only a slight swelling was found.

The study showed that the body weight of three - month-old white rats that received severe polytrauma in experimental group 2 ranged from 127 to 150 g, with an average of 134 g. Morphological and morphometric characteristics of kidney of rats during the period of K transmission, day 3 after severe polytrauma: absolute weight of kidneys - from 826.2 mg to 1032.2 mg, average - 834.43 ± 16.1 mg; length - from 15.4 to 18.14 mm, average - 15.83 ± 0.7 mm, width - from 5.8 mm to 8.56 mm, average value - 6.84 ± 0.4 mm; thickness - from 7.11 mm to 8.24 mm, average - 6.72 ± 0.6 mm; the volume of the kidney was from 400.84 mm^3 to 674.92 mm^3 , the average was $541.9 \pm 29.9 \text{ mm}^3$.

The area of kidney bodies is from $2112 \mu\text{m}^2$ to $2412.87 \mu\text{m}^2$, the average is $2269.62 \pm 24.23 \mu\text{m}^2$; the area of the vascular ball is from $1778.3 \mu\text{m}^2$ to $2000.4 \mu\text{m}^2$, the average is $1923.67 \pm 16.8 \mu\text{m}^2$; it was noted that the area of the capsule cavity is $336.32 \mu\text{m}^2$ to $363.2 \mu\text{m}^2$, the average is $366.6 \pm 4.4 \mu\text{m}^2$. The diameter of the proximal convoluted tubular tubules is from $29.22 \mu\text{m}$ to $33.68 \mu\text{m}$, the average is $33.11 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{m}$, the diameter of the tubular cavity is from $16.12 \mu\text{m}$ to $26.45 \mu\text{m}$, the average is $17,21 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{m}$. The diameter of the distal convoluted tubules is from $27.44 \mu\text{m}$ to $33.4 \mu\text{m}$, the average is $31.12 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$, the diameter of the tubular cavity is from $14.1 \mu\text{m}$ to $18.31 \mu\text{m}$, the average is 16, It was equal to $0.3 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$.

Thus, as a result of macroscopic , histological and histomorphometric studies, severe polytrauma of the experimental group received A number of morphological changes were detected in the kidneys of 3- month-old white rats . Macroscopically , no obvious changes were observed in the kidneys of white rats with severe polytrauma. Only a little swelling was found. Histological examination showed that on the 1st day after severe polytrauma, a number of

specific changes were detected in the structure of nephrons of rat kidneys. In this case, the basal layer of the kidney has retained its structure in the nephrons and is enlarged due to the expansion of the renal corpuscle, the vascular ball of the kidney, and the Shumlyansky-Bowman capsule. This situation indicates that the filtration processes in it have decreased. At the same time, changes were observed in proximal and distal e-gray tubercles of nephrons under the influence of severe polytrauma.

Morphometric the results of the analysis showed that after severe polytrauma, the area of the renal corpuscle, the area of the kidney ball, the area of the Shumlyansky-Bowman capsule, the diameter of the proximal and distal convoluted tubules, and the diameter of the tubule space in the kidney nephrons were found to be enlarged. Histological results was confirmed by histomorphometric parameters and statistically significant differences were found compared to the parameters of the control group animals

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